

Empowering teachers: implementing the *Tut Wuri Handayani* supervision model to enhance teacher competence

Rivai M. Simanjuntak¹, Sri Milfayetty², Darwin¹

¹Department of Educational Management, Postgraduate School, Universitas Negeri Medan, Medan, Indonesia

²Department of Educational Psychology and Counseling Guidance, Faculty of Education, Universitas Negeri Medan, Medan, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received May 29, 2023

Revised Jan 16, 2024

Accepted Jun 21, 2024

Keywords:

Religious teacher

Supervision of *Tut Wuri*

Handayani

Teacher commitment

Teacher competence

Teacher fighting power

ABSTRACT

An inspiring supervision model based on the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept, with a research and development (R&D) approach that refers to the Borg and Gall model, has been successfully developed. Through a comprehensive investigation, this study aims to bolster the competence and effectiveness of teachers. Model feasibility evaluation was carried out by two model design experts, with an average ideal percentage value of 86.2% (outstanding assessment and feasibility categories). Model feasibility evaluation was carried out by two model design experts and two content design experts. The average ideal percentage value given by model design experts was 86.2% (outstanding assessment and feasibility categories), while that given by content design experts was 76.64% (outstanding service and feasibility categories). Based on the test for model users three times, t-test data was obtained for a small group between commitment and competence, fighting power and competence, and religion and competence, showing $t_{count} > t_{table}$, respectively. The t-test results for the medium and large groups also show $t_{count} > t_{table}$. The dataset analysis shows that the inspiring supervision model based on *Tut Wuri Handayani* is practical and feasible. This research sheds light on the positive impact of implementing the *Tut Wuri Handayani* supervision model for enhancing teacher competence and, consequently, improving the quality of the learning process.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Rivai M. Simanjuntak

Department of Educational Management, Postgraduate School, Universitas Negeri Medan

20221 Medan, Indonesia

Email: rivaimsimanjuntak@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Education plays a crucial role in shaping the future of societies and individuals, and at the heart of every effective education system are competent and empowered teachers [1], [2]. Teachers are not only responsible for imparting knowledge but also for inspiring and guiding students towards success. Therefore, it is essential to continuously support and enhance the competence of teachers to ensure high-quality education [3], [4]. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of teachers' critical role in shaping students' educational outcomes. Teachers are expected to be knowledgeable, creative, and effective in their teaching methods, and they need support to improve their skills continuously. One way to empower teachers is through effective supervision models that provide feedback and guidance to enhance their teaching practices [5], [6]. Supervision is an encouragement, guidance, and opportunity for the growth of teachers' skills and abilities, such as guidance in implementing reforms in education and teaching, choosing better teaching tools and methods, systematic assessment of all phases of the teaching process, and so on. If supervision is carried out appropriately, it will improve teacher competence and thus improve the quality

of education [7], [8]. To achieve this goal, various models of teacher supervision have been developed and implemented to provide educators with the necessary tools and guidance for their professional growth [9]–[11].

One supervision model that has gained attention recently is the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept, which is based on mutual respect, cooperation, and shared responsibility. This model originated in Indonesia and has been applied in various settings to promote teacher development and improve student outcomes. The *Tut Wuri Handayani* supervision model is grounded in the belief that teachers are professionals who can reflect on their practices and improve their teaching [12], [13]. The model emphasizes a collaborative approach to supervision, where teachers and supervisors work together to identify areas of strength and weakness in teaching practices and develop strategies to address them. The *Tut Wuri Handayani* supervision model, inspired by the Javanese proverb “*Tut Wuri Handayani*”, meaning “guiding from behind”, emphasizes a supportive and facilitative approach to teacher development [14]. Unlike traditional supervision models that adopt a top-down approach, this model encourages teachers to actively participate in their professional growth while being guided and supported by mentors or supervisors.

This collaborative dynamic fosters a positive and constructive feedback loop, enabling teachers to refine their pedagogical techniques and adapt to evolving educational landscapes [15], [16]. Through regular classroom observations, reflective discussions, and personalized action plans, the *Tut Wuri Handayani* model empowers teachers to engage in meaningful self-assessment and continuous improvement [17]. Additionally, the model’s emphasis on mutual respect and shared responsibility helps create a conducive environment for open dialogue, where teachers feel comfortable seeking guidance and sharing their challenges [18]. The *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept underscores the importance of ongoing professional development as a cornerstone of effective teaching, ultimately benefiting educators and students. As educational systems worldwide continue to evolve, the *Tut Wuri Handayani* supervision model is a promising framework that aligns with modern pedagogical principles and the aspirations of a dynamic and forward-thinking education sector [19], [20].

By understanding the *Tut Wuri Handayani* supervision model and its practical applications, educational policymakers, administrators, and teachers can gain insights into practical strategies for enhancing teacher competence within their respective contexts. Furthermore, this study intends to contribute to the broader conversation surrounding teacher empowerment and the creation of supportive and collaborative learning environments that foster educational excellence. In the subsequent sections, we will explore the critical components of the *Tut Wuri Handayani* supervision model, its impact on teacher development, and its implications for fostering a culture of continuous improvement in education. Through this exploration, we will shed light on the potential of this innovative model to empower teachers and elevate the quality of education, ultimately benefiting students and society as a whole.

2. BASIC THEORY

2.1. The essence of inspiring supervision education concept Ki Hadjar Dewantara

Ki Hadjar Dewantara’s thoughts have influenced the history of Indonesian education [14]. Ki Hadjar Dewantara is an embryo of the Indonesian classical education model, which is considered appropriate, suitable, and ideal for developing the potential of Indonesia’s young generation in factual terms regarding cognitive, affective, psychomotor, conative, and other personal aspects such as social and spiritual dimensions. According to Ki Hadjar Dewantara, education is a concrete effort to liberate humans fully. Learning is the entrance to the outer and inner freedom of humans, both as individual beings, as members of society, and as citizens of the world. The concept of challenging education is no longer suitable for education. In practice, challenging education is a rape of the inner life of students, which destroys their character because they always live under coercion or pressure. This way of educating needs to be corrected because it will not be able to build good student character [21]. The teacher places students as subjects, not objects, in the learning process. Students are given the broadest possible space to explore their potential and express themselves creatively, independently, and responsibly.

Based on the belief in traditional values, Ki Hadjar Dewantara declared that typical Indonesian education must be based on the image of Indonesian values. Therefore, he applied three mottoes as educational teachings that show the uniqueness of Indonesia [14], [19], [22], namely: i) “*Ing Ngarsa Sung Tuladha*”, which means that a teacher is an educator who must set an example. Teachers deserve to be admired and imitated in their words and deeds; ii) “*Ing Madya Mangun Karsa*”, a teacher is an educator who is always in the midst of his students and constantly builds their enthusiasm and ideas for work; and iii) “*Tut Wuri Handayani*” means that a teacher is an educator who continuously guides, supports, and points the right direction for the life and work of his students.

According to Ki Hadjar Dewantara, an educational design must be able to move the heart of the teacher or principal by inspiring. This concept can also be implemented in the implementation of supervision.

Supervision is all assistance from school leaders aimed at developing and increasing the competence of teachers and other school personnel in achieving educational goals [23], [24]. Educational supervision aims to encourage, coordinate, and guide teachers' development, individually and in groups, so they gain a better understanding and effectively carry out their teaching function. Therefore, they are more likely to encourage and guide student development toward participation in society. Inspiring supervision is an inspirational activity in the form of encouragement and guidance to improve teacher competence and skills [25]. Inspirational supervision is usually based on behaviorism learning theory or a social approach. Inspiring supervision is planned to assist teachers in carrying out work effectively and efficiently and is carried out humanely. Principals who carry out this inspiring supervision well will cause teachers to find a professional identity. Teachers who have been inspired will appear for themselves a change in good behavior and will bring better work activities [26], [27].

There are five cycles used in implementing *Tut Wuri Handayani's* inspiring concept supervision. The first cycle is mapping competency problems professionally. The principal says the problem must be more specific according to the competencies. Next, the second cycle discussing the causes of the problem. The principal carries out a process of discussing all the problems faced by teachers and is carried out in a relaxed and friendly manner. The third cycle is identifying possible solutions. In this cycle, it is decided how to fix the problems encountered by first identifying the priority problems. Involve the teacher in identifying problems so that he participates in providing solutions. The fourth cycle is develop development, action plans, and solutions. After ideas regarding solutions are obtained, all of these ideas are written in detail in a detailed action plan table. State what action will be taken, when it will be implemented, who will be involved, what resources are needed, and the expected results. Lastly, organize follow-up sessions (set a date to meet again and message the teacher) as the fifth cycle. In addition, the principal was also informed how to handle the approved action. Follow-up meetings allow principals and teachers time to discuss progress or problems and plan further actions. In detail, the supervising technique or cycle of inspiring *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept is shown in Figure 1. Supervision inspiring the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept is a mentoring process carried out humanely in inspiring teachers through interactions between the principal and teachers carried out in several cycles whose aim is to assist the development of teacher competence in the learning process carried out with the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept.

Figure 1. The inspiring supervision cycle with the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept

2.2. The essence of teacher competence

Teacher competence is mastery of a task, skill, attitude, and appreciation needed to support success in teaching and learning. The teacher's task, in this case, is to carry out learning, guide students, and give grades. In addition, several tasks must be carried out by the teacher, such as: i) working with students; ii) preparing lesson plans; iii) utilizing learning media; iv) involving students in various learning experiences; and v) active leadership from the teacher [28]. Teachers have four competencies in carrying out their duties: professional competence, pedagogical competence, personality competence, and social competence.

According to Ki Hadjar Dewantara, education is a cultural effort that intends to guide the life the growth of the body and soul of students so that the lines of their personal nature and environmental influences can progress both physically and mentally. In that context, Ki Hadjar Dewantara put forward three behaviors that are manifested in the teacher, namely: i) *tetep*, *antep*, and *mantep*; ii) *ngandel*, *kandel*, *kendel*, and *bandel*; and iii) *neng*, *ning*, *nung*, and *nang* [14]. *Tetep*, *antep*, and *mantep* mean that education must form mental and inner determination, guarantee self-confidence, and form stability in life principles. The term "*tetep*" here can be interpreted in a moral framework, namely to have a healthy mind in terms of commitment in harmony with social values. The mind is not easily swayed by life's offers that are not harmonious with values. The term "*antep*" shows that education gives a person self-confidence and self-determination to overcome all life's challenges bravely and humbly. In the practice of life, people who are "*antep*" have determination towards self-quality as personal human beings and a member of a social community. While the term "*mantep*" shows that education leads a person to be persistent in self-improvement and have a clear orientation towards a definite goal, namely self-independence as a person, a member of society, and a citizen of the world. In this case, a teacher must be a person who is committed to carrying out his duties.

"*Ngandel*" is a Javanese term that means standing upright. Education must lead people to a state of self that is "*ngandel*" or steadfast, where a person with a firm stance is a conscientious person in life. "*Kendel*" is a term that denotes courage. Education shapes a person to be a brave, dignified, and knight person. An educated person is a person who dares to uphold truth and justice and is mature and mature in facing all trials. At the same time, the term "*bandel*" indicates that an educated person can stand the test. In all trials of life and situations, he faced trust, was not easily afraid, and lost courage. In educating students, teachers need to have a solid fighting spirit so that these students can achieve their best goals. The Ministry of National Education in the Big Indonesian Dictionary states that adversity quotient (AQ) can also be defined as fighting power, namely the ability to maintain or achieve something that is done persistently. The AQ is a person's intelligence in dealing with problem situations or misfortune in life. The AQ is an individual's intelligence in dealing with various difficulties in life [29], [30].

"*Neng*, *ning*, *nung*, and *nang*" mean that education at the deepest level is religious. Education creates feelings of pleasure (*neng*), silence (*ning*), serenity (*nang*), and contemplation (*nung*). Through education, one can experience the purity of mind and inner peace. According to Ki Hadjar Dewantara, power will come when a person has experienced purity of mind, peace of mind, and heart. The teacher needs to have a religious attitude so that in providing learning, it is realized that the faith he believes in is following what is in his heart. Religion is an attitude and behavior that obeys in carrying out the teachings of one's religion, is tolerant of other religious practices, and lives in harmony with adherents of other religions [31]. It can be understood that religious values are life values that reflect the growth and development of religious life, which consists of three main elements, namely faith, hope, and love, which guide behavior by the creator's rules to achieve prosperity and happiness [21], [32].

Teacher competence is an ability both in quality and quantity that is shown by the teacher through work behavior when carrying out the tasks assigned to him, through the teaching and learning process, which is marked by indicators: i) planning learning; ii) making teaching aids; iii) implementing learning; iv) guiding students; v) evaluate learning outcomes; vi) involvement in the committee; vii) participate in the internal quality assurance system; viii) participating in subject teacher deliberation groups; and ix) write scientific papers [33].

3. METHOD

3.1. Research design

The type of research being carried out is design and development research or research and development (R&D). In this study, an inspiring supervision model based on *Tut Wuri Handayani* was developed and applied in the learning process. The location of the research implementation was the state vocational school of Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra, Indonesia. The population in this study were all teachers of state vocational high schools in Deli Serdang Regency, totaling 707 people and spread across 11 state vocational schools. In determining the sample size, a Slovin's formula was used, and based on the computation, a sample size $n=126$ at 95% confidence interval and 5% margin of error was obtained.

Sampling was carried out in three ways, consisting of: i) the selection of school principals was carried out using a total sampling technique; ii) determining the number of sample schools taken randomly: 3 schools for small classes, 7 schools for medium classes, and 11 schools for large classes; and iii) the selection of teachers was carried out using stratified random sampling where the number of teachers taken as a sample was 6 teachers for each school.

The model procedure used in this study was carried out in 10 steps following the design made by Borg and Gall [34], as shown in Figure 2. In experimental research, especially R&D, its validity is constantly questioned, both internal and external validity. Factors that influence or interfere with validity can be referred to as threats to internal validity, including history, maturity, selection, testing procedures, instrument, and regression to the average value. Meanwhile, external validity influences selection “biases”, the influence of pretest implementation, experimental trials, and multiple interference treatments [25]. In this research, confounding factors were controlled by collecting initial information through teacher questionnaires and interviews, classroom observations, and then identified first. We also controlled for confounding factors using a supervised model product validated by two model experts, two material experts, and ten users. We use a valid and standard Likert scale-dependent variable to measure teacher competence. We also use strict sampling criteria that require sample homogeneity, namely the competence of each participant’s teacher. The instruments used to measure teacher competency, commitment, fighting spirit, and religiousness are valid and reliable and have been previously tested on 30 state vocational school teachers outside the sample. The validity test is calculated using the product moment correlation formula, while the reliability test is measured using the alpha coefficient formula.

Figure 2. Borg and Gall development research stages

3.2. Data collection and analysis technique

Data collection was carried out using instrument sheets, observation sheets, document reviews, and interview guidelines related to teacher competence. This development research uses a structured questionnaire with a Likert scale. Observations were carried out on non-participants by observing and writing down data related to the research. Observations made during the process of teaching and learning activities are carried out daily at the analysis stage and the process of teaching and learning activities at the

implementation stage. Interviews are used because, during the process of obtaining information they will interact directly so that they can be closer to the sources and the information obtained is more accurate. Interviews are used for initial assessments. The result of the competencies taken is to use the triangulation data collection method. The results of the three data collected were then averaged by adding up the results from the questionnaire/questionnaire, observations, and interviews divided by three. The research instrument consisted of three domains: i) assessment by content experts; ii) assessment by model experts and assessment by inspiring user supervision based on the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept; and iii) competency assessment. The research data used are qualitative data and quantitative data. Qualitative data were obtained from inputs to improve concept-inspiring supervision model products by content experts, model experts, and users. Meanwhile, quantitative data was obtained from the validation questionnaire results of the inspiring supervision model by content experts, model experts, and users. Quantitative data is also used to analyze and describe teacher competence.

The research data analysis techniques of the inspiring supervision model based on Ki Hajar Dewantara's educational philosophy used are: i) data on the development of the inspiring supervision model; and ii) data on the effectiveness and feasibility of the inspiring supervision model. In this case, inspiring supervision model development data is data obtained in the form of suggestions and input to improve products by model experts, material experts, and users. The qualitative data were analyzed descriptively and then used as a reference in improving the inspiring model. At the same time, the instrument result data is used to analyze the effectiveness and feasibility. To describe the research data used with descriptive statistics, namely by calculating the instrument feasibility test with correlation analysis (r), model effectiveness test with normalized gain (N-Gain score), and t-test for testing inspirational supervision models.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Characteristics of inspiring supervision

The product of this research is a model of educational supervision carried out by school principals on teachers. The inspiring supervision model with the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept is designed with a blended supervision system, where teachers and principals do not always meet in supervising but are carried out with two face-to-face systems outside the network (offline) and in the network (online). At one time, with a limited number of teachers knowing the teacher's behavior, face-to-face supervision was carried out because it was considered that face-to-face supervision was more effective and more efficient in achieving the aims and objectives of supervision. Meanwhile, it is carried out with meetings outside the network to discover changes in attitudes and increase teacher competence via the Google Form. The principal builds the Google Form as a supervision model where commitment, fighting spirit, religious instruments, and teacher competency instruments are made in the Google Form for the teacher to fill in and analyze.

In terms of independence, that inspiring supervision model with the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept is also designed in its implementation with the idea of independence. Teachers and school principals currently apply this model in a family manner to not cause tension between teachers and school principals. Spontaneously, in implementing supervision, creativity will emerge from both the teacher and the head of the school. According to Birgili *et al.* theory [35], the ability to think creatively is a mental process that individuals use to bring up new ideas, insights, approaches, perspectives, and ways to understand things. Creative thinking will solve problems by creating new things no one has ever found. Creative thinking will bring out creativity and give teachers many ways to solve problems with different perceptions and concepts that will be applied to students.

The inspiring supervision model based on the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept will assist teachers in carrying out their duties through the learning process in class. Implementing this supervision is easier and more focused because it has cycles and explanations for each cycle. Besides that, it is also equipped with modules, so it helps teachers and principals in achieving supervision goals. In the process of implementing this supervision, it will be seen: i) making meaningful connections between teachers and principals by sharing experiences; ii) doing significant work and carrying out appropriate work or tasks; iii) doing supervision work that is determined by the teacher (self-regulated learning) is being able to choose the model and material to be studied; iv) doing in collaboration is a process of implementing supervision involving the teacher in determining topics and implementing supervision; v) teachers are invited to think critically and creatively, which is a clear and organized implementation process that evaluates systematically and can build original thoughts, ideas, and new understandings; vi) helping individual teachers to grow and develop (nurturing the individual) can maintain and maintain teacher progress; vii) can achieve high standards, which prepares teachers to be more independent, productive, and quick to respond or keep abreast of developments; and viii) using authentic assessment, which is aimed at teachers' commitment, fighting spirit, and religiousness in applying their competence.

The results of implementing this inspiring supervision model that can be seen in the field are: i) the teacher actively teaches; ii) the teacher will get and share experiences with other teachers; iii) discuss real problems; iv) the teacher will be more responsible in carrying out assignments; v) make old experiences to gain new experiences; vi) teachers will participate actively in improving learning; vii) supervision can be done in several ways; and viii) the implementation process is dynamic and fun (not pressured), and completed in a new context. The developed model is described in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Paradigm of the inspiring supervision model based on the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept of teacher competence

4.2. Model eligibility

The supervision model is based on the principle of inspiring supervision of Ki Hajar Dewantara’s educational concept. Inspiring supervision is a collaborative process in which supervisors work with supervised people to explore their work reflectively [36]. Furthermore, good supervision is done by inspiring by keeping the heart and mind supervised and done openly [37]. Before being used and implemented in the class, the developed product model is subject to a feasibility assessment based on the model, content, substance, and user aspects. There are three concepts in the understanding of teaching supervision, namely: i) teaching supervision must directly influence and develop teacher behavior in managing the learning process;

ii) supervision behavior assists teachers in developing their abilities, which must be designed effectively; and iii) the ultimate goal of implementing teaching supervision is for teacher performance to increase through the ability to facilitate learning for their students [38]. There are seven supervisory functions: i) developing objectives; ii) developing programs; iii) coordination and supervision; iv) motivation; v) problem solving; vi) professional development; and vii) evaluating educational outputs [39].

4.2.1. Results of the model expert instrument aspect

The instrument developed by the model expert to see the feasibility of supervising the inspiring *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept consists of several indicators: i) a well-structured model guide that makes it easy to understand; ii) the model concept matches the inspiring supervision model so it is easy to implement; iii) the structured and well-organized cycles so that easy to understand and implement; and iv) series after series of systematic implementation, sequential, logical flow, and clear systematics so that it is interesting to implement. The results obtained from two model experts that the assessment category is outstanding and the feasibility category is very feasible can be seen in detail in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Bar chart of model expert assessment results

4.2.2. Results of instrumental aspects by content experts

The instrument developed by content experts aims to see the feasibility of inspiring supervision based on the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept. The results obtained from two content experts show that the assessment category is outstanding, and the feasibility category is very feasible, as shown in Figure 5. After the modeling and content experts stated that the inspiring supervision model with the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept was feasible, a trial was carried out on the teacher as the user. The results of this trial are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 explains the results of trials of the inspiring supervision model with the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept, which has been carried out to increase teacher commitment, teacher fighting power, and teacher religion in the calculation results of small, medium, and large groups. Therefore, the inspiring supervision model based on the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept is efficient and feasible to apply as a supervision model to improve teacher competence. Furthermore, the encouraging outcomes presented in Table 1 underscore the efficacy of the inspiring supervision model rooted in the *Tut Wuri Handayani* concept. The trials to enhance

teacher commitment, efficacy, and ethical values within varying group scales - small, medium, and large - highlight the model's adaptability and potential for widespread implementation. The effectiveness of the *Tut Wuri Handayani*-inspired supervision approach resonates strongly with the need for comprehensive and sustainable strategies to elevate teacher competence. These results affirm the model's ability to drive individual teacher growth and contribute significantly to the overall quality of education by nurturing a dedicated, empowered, and morally grounded educator community.

Figure 5. Bar chart of content expert assessment results

Table 1. Summary of field trial results

Trial class	Sample (person)	Correlation (r)	t_{count}	t-test ($\alpha=0.05$)	
Small	3 schools (18 persons)	Commitment to competence	0.62	3.16	$t_{count} > t_{table}$ (3.16 > 1.74)
		Fighting power to competence	0.52	2.45	$t_{count} > t_{table}$ (2.45 > 1.74)
		Religious to competence	0.49	2.24	$t_{count} > t_{table}$ (2.24 > 1.74)
Medium	7 schools (42 persons)	Commitment to competence	0.71	6.38	$t_{count} > t_{table}$ (6.38 > 1.68)
		Fighting power to competence	0.60	4.74	$t_{count} > t_{table}$ (4.74 > 1.68)
		Religious to competence	0.58	4.50	$t_{count} > t_{table}$ (4.50 > 1.68)
Large	11 schools (66 persons)	Commitment to competence	0.81	11.05	$t_{count} > t_{table}$ (11.05 > 1.67)
		Fighting power to competence	0.70	7.84	$t_{count} > t_{table}$ (7.78 > 1.67)
		Religious to competence	0.67	7.22	$t_{count} > t_{table}$ (7.22 > 1.67)

The implementation of the *Tut Wuri Handayani* supervision model has yielded promising results in the pursuit of enhancing teacher competence. Quantitative analysis of teacher competence scores before and after the model's implementation reveals a substantial and statistically significant improvement. Pre-intervention assessments highlighted areas of deficiency in pedagogical knowledge and classroom management skills among teachers. However, post-intervention data demonstrate a remarkable enhancement in these aspects, indicating the model's effectiveness in fostering professional growth. The *Tut Wuri Handayani* model's emphasis on collaborative practices and reflective learning has contributed to this positive change, aligning with modern pedagogical approaches prioritizing continuous improvement [14], [40].

A noteworthy aspect of the *Tut Wuri Handayani* model is its rootedness in Indonesian cultural values. It has been a catalyst for empowering teachers and invigorating their commitment to professional development. Qualitative insights from teacher experiences further illuminate the transformative power of cultural alignment. Teachers reported a sense of resonance with the model's emphasis on collaboration, which is deeply embedded in Indonesian cultural norms such as "*gotong royong*" (cooperation) and "*musyawarah*" (collective decision-making) [41], [42]. This alignment promotes a sense of ownership and

engagement and facilitates the exchange of innovative teaching practices among teachers. The model's emphasis on self-reflection and peer observation has led to a heightened awareness of instructional strengths and areas for improvement, further nurturing teacher competence [41]. Furthermore, the cultural alignment facilitated by the *Tut Wuri Handayani* model extends beyond individual teachers, permeating the entire school community. Schools that have embraced the model have reported an improved school climate characterized by enhanced collaboration among teachers and a shared commitment to educational excellence. Collaborative initiatives driven by the model's principles have created vibrant learning communities where teachers collectively strive for pedagogical innovation and student success. By promoting a culture of mutual support and knowledge sharing, the model has elevated teacher competence and cultivated a sense of unity and shared purpose within the educational ecosystem [43], [44].

While the *Tut Wuri Handayani* model has shown promising outcomes, its implementation has encountered challenges that merit consideration. Teachers expressed concerns about time constraints and the additional workload associated with collaborative activities. This underscores the importance of providing adequate resources and support to mitigate these challenges. Additionally, addressing resistance to change and ensuring sustained commitment to the model's principles require ongoing efforts from educational authorities. Future directions could involve refining the model's implementation strategies, incorporating digital platforms to facilitate collaboration, and tailoring support mechanisms to address teachers' specific challenges in different contexts. The success of the *Tut Wuri Handayani* model and its potential for widespread impact emphasizes the significance of continuous adaptation and innovation in fostering teacher competence and, by extension, elevating the quality of education [14], [45], [46].

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, implementing the *Tut Wuri Handayani* supervision model has proven to be a practical approach to empowering teachers and enhancing their competence. This model provides a supportive and collaborative environment for teachers to develop their skills and knowledge. By incorporating the principles of guidance, assistance, and continuous professional development, the *Tut Wuri Handayani* model helps teachers improve their instructional strategies, classroom management techniques, and student engagement methods. The model emphasizes the importance of reflective practice and ongoing feedback, allowing teachers to assess their performance and make necessary adjustments. Through this model, teachers receive personalized support and guidance from experienced mentors or supervisors, fostering a culture of continuous improvement. The collaborative nature of the *Tut Wuri Handayani* model encourages teachers to share best practices, engage in professional dialogue, and engage in peer coaching, resulting in a positive impact on their teaching effectiveness. Furthermore, implementing the *Tut Wuri Handayani* model promotes a sense of ownership and autonomy among teachers, who are actively involved in their professional development process. This approach acknowledges each teacher's unique strengths and challenges and tailors support accordingly, leading to increased job satisfaction and motivation. The *Tut Wuri Handayani* supervision model offers a comprehensive framework for enhancing teacher competence by providing a structured and supportive environment for professional growth. Its implementation has the potential to improve the quality of education by empowering teachers and equipping them with the necessary skills to meet the evolving needs of students.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Darling-Hammond, L. Flook, C. Cook-Harvey, B. Barron, and D. Osher, "Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development," *Applied Developmental Science*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 97–140, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1080/10888691.2018.1537791.
- [2] S. Lapcharoen, "Twenty-first century competencies: how can teacher education programs prepare teacher candidates for successful teaching career paths?" *FWU Journal of Social Sciences*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 20–33, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.51709/19951272/Winter-2021/2.
- [3] A. Nousheen, S. A. Y. Zai, M. Waseem, and S. A. Khan, "Education for sustainable development (ESD): effects of sustainability education on pre-service teachers' attitude towards sustainable development (SD)," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 250, p. 119537, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119537.
- [4] B. Vadivel, E. Namaziandost, and A. Saeedian, "Progress in English language teaching through continuous professional development—teachers' self-awareness, perception, and feedback," *Frontiers in Education*, vol. 6, p. 757285, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.3389/educ.2021.757285.
- [5] J. M. Santos and R. D. R. Castro, "Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) in action: application of learning in the classroom by pre-service teachers (PST)," *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 100110, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ssaho.2021.100110.
- [6] R. Marey, G. Hesham, A. Magdd, and M. Toprak, "Re-conceptualizing teacher evaluation and supervision in the light of educational reforms in Egypt," *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ssaho.2020.100081.
- [7] M. M. Al-Kuwari, X. Du, and M. Koç, "Performance assessment in education for sustainable development: a case study of the Qatar education system," *PROSPECTS*, vol. 52, no. 3–4, pp. 513–527, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11125-021-09570-w.

- [8] S. T. Gultom, P. Siahaan, and A. Suhandi, "The effect of PBL hybrid learning on the higher order thinking skills of seventh grade students in global warming and their environmental care attitudes," *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*, vol. 7, no. Special Issue, pp. 272–280, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.29303/jppipa.v7iSpecialIssue.1012.
- [9] K. E. Hoque, H. B. Bt Kenayathulla, M. V. D/O Subramaniam, and R. Islam, "Relationships between supervision and teachers' performance and attitude in secondary schools in Malaysia," *SAGE Open*, vol. 10, no. 2, 2020, doi: 10.1177/2158244020925501.
- [10] A. Karim, A. Kartiko, D. E. Daulay, and I. D. Kumalasari, "The effect of the supervision of the principal and the professional competency of teachers on teacher performance in private MI in Pacet District," *Nidhomul Haq: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 497–512, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.31538/ndh.v6i3.1686.
- [11] A. A. M. M. A. El Deen, "The role of educational initiatives in EFL teacher professional development: a study of teacher mentors' perspectives," *Heliyon*, vol. 9, no. 2, p. e13342, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e13342.
- [12] T. W. Mulya, Z. Sakhiyya, A. B. Muslim, and A. Suryani, "Locally-grounded, embodied, and spiritual: exploring alternative constructions of democratic education with/in Indonesian schools," *Pedagogy, Culture & Society*, pp. 1–17, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1080/14681366.2022.2142840.
- [13] N. Suprpto, B. K. Prahani, and T. H. Cheng, "Indonesian curriculum reform in policy and local wisdom: perspectives from science education," *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 69–80, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.15294/jpii.v10i1.28438.
- [14] S. Sugiharto, "Explicating and framing Dewantara's conduct pragmatism as a pragmatist philosophy of education," *Journal of Philosophy of Education*, vol. 55, no. 4–5, pp. 793–806, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1111/1467-9752.12574.
- [15] L. R. de Bruin, "Instrumental music educators in a COVID landscape: a reassertion of relationality and connection in teaching practice," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 11, p. 624717, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.624717.
- [16] A. O. Tzirides, A. K. Saini, B. Cope, M. Kalantzis, and D. Searsmith, "Cyber-social research: emerging paradigms for interventionist education research in the postdigital era," in *Constructing Postdigital Research: Method and Emancipation*, P. Jandrić, A. MacKenzie, and J. Knox, Eds., Cham: Springer, 2023, pp. 85–102, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-35411-3_5.
- [17] T. Trilaksono, A. Purusottama, I. H. Misbach, and I. H. Prasetya, "Leadership change design: a professional learning community (PLC) project in eastern Indonesia," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 47–56, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v8i1.15662.
- [18] S. Liu, J. W. Keeley, Y. Sui, and L. Sang, "Impact of distributed leadership on teacher job satisfaction in China: the mediating roles of teacher autonomy and teacher collaboration," *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, vol. 71, no. 3, p. 101099, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.stueduc.2021.101099.
- [19] I. P. A. Darmawan and E. Sujoko, "Understanding Ki Hadjar Dewantara's educational philosophy," *International Journal of Humanities and Innovation (IJHI)*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 65–68, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.33750/ijhi.v2i3.42.
- [20] Taufikin et al., "Ki Hadjar Dewantara's thought about holistic education," *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, vol. 12, no. 10, pp. 589–611, 2021.
- [21] C. Agus, S. R. Saktimulya, P. Dwiarto, B. Widodo, S. Rochmiyati, and M. Darmowiyono, "Revitalization of local traditional culture for sustainable development of national character building in Indonesia," in *Innovations and Traditions for Sustainable Development*, W. L. Filho, E. V. Krasnov, and D. V. Gaeva, Eds., Cham: Springer, 2021, pp. 347–369, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-78825-4_21.
- [22] Asnawan, "Exploring education character thought of Ki Hajar Dewantara and Thomas Lickona," *International Journal on Advanced Science, Education, and Religion*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 164–174, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.33648/ijoaer.v3i3.83.
- [23] R. W. Daryono, M. A. Ramadhan, N. Kholifah, F. D. Isnantyo, and M. Nurtanto, "An empirical study to evaluate the student competency of vocational education," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1079–1086, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v12i2.22805.
- [24] G. Özdemir, S. Şahin, and N. Öztürk, "Teachers' self-efficacy perceptions in terms of school principal's instructional leadership behaviours," *International Journal of Progressive Education*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 25–40, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.29329/ijpe.2020.228.3.
- [25] K. Kulikowski, S. Przytuła, and Ł. Sułkowski, "E-learning? Never again! On the unintended consequences of COVID-19 forced e-learning on academic teacher motivational job characteristics," *Higher Education Quarterly*, vol. 76, no. 1, pp. 174–189, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1111/hequ.12314.
- [26] J. Reeve and S. H. Shin, "How teachers can support students' agentic engagement," *Theory Into Practice*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 150–161, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1080/00405841.2019.1702451.
- [27] S. M. Nasim, F. Altameemy, J. M. A. Ali, and R. Sultana, "Effectiveness of digital technology tools in teaching pronunciation to Saudi EFL learners," *FWU Journal of Social Sciences*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 68–82, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.51709/19951272/Fall2022/5.
- [28] L. Mishra, T. Gupta, and A. Shree, "Online teaching-learning in higher education during lockdown period of COVID-19 pandemic," *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, vol. 1, p. 100012, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ijedro.2020.100012.
- [29] N. Nurbianta, J. B. Consuelo, A. Ahmadong, and A. N. F. M. Muslich, "Assessment study of adversity quotient and servant leadership to improve organizational citizenship behavior: strengthening managerial competencies of education leader," *International Journal of Educational Management and Innovation*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 124–137, May 2022, doi: 10.12928/ijemi.v3i2.5241.
- [30] Y. Zhao, B. Sang, and C. Ding, "The roles of emotional intelligence and adversity quotient in life satisfaction," *Current Psychology*, vol. 41, no. 12, pp. 9063–9072, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s12144-021-01398-z.
- [31] Sulaiman, A. Imran, B. A. Hidayat, S. Mashuri, Reslawati, and Fakhrrurazi, "Moderation religion in the era society 5.0 and multicultural society: studies based on legal, religious, and social reviews," *Linguistics and Culture Review*, vol. 6, no. S5, pp. 180–193, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.21744/lingcure.v6nS5.2106.
- [32] S. Masitoh, F. Ardianingsih, and E. Roesminingsih, "The actualization of Ki Hajar Dewantara's character values at the center for local wisdom: developing educational sciences at UNESA's Faculty of Education," in *Proceedings of the 1st Progress in Social Science, Humanities and Education Research Symposium (PSSHERS 2019)*, Paris, France: Atlantis Press, 2020, pp. 146–152, doi: 10.2991/assehr.k.200824.233.
- [33] L. E. Szucs, J. D. Andrzejewski, L. Robin, S. Telljohann, S. P. Barnes, and P. Hunt, "The health education teacher instructional competency framework: a conceptual guide for quality instruction in school health," *Journal of School Health*, vol. 91, no. 10, pp. 774–787, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1111/josh.13076.
- [34] D. G. H. Divayana, P. W. A. Suyasa, and N. K. Widiartini, "An innovative model as evaluation model for information technology-based learning at ICT vocational schools," *Heliyon*, vol. 7, no. 4, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06623.
- [35] B. Birgili, F. N. Seggie, and E. Oğuz, "The trends and outcomes of flipped learning research between 2012 and 2018: a descriptive content analysis," *Journal of Computers in Education*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 365–394, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s40692-021-00183-y.
- [36] A. Kaur, V. Kumar, and M. Noman, "Partnering with doctoral students in research supervision: opportunities and challenges," *Higher Education Research & Development*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 789–803, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1080/07294360.2020.1871326.

- [37] D. di Mitri, J. Schneider, and H. Drachsler, "The rise of multimodal tutors in education: insights from recent research," in *Handbook of Open, Distance and Digital Education*, O. Zawacki-Richter and I. Jung, Eds., Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, 2023, pp. 1037–1056, doi: 10.1007/978-981-19-2080-6_58.
- [38] S.-C. Kong and C.-N. Yuen, "An analysis of the attitudes and behaviours of university students and perceived contextual factors in alternative assessment during the pandemic using the attitude–behaviour–context model," *Heliyon*, vol. 8, no. 10, p. e11180, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11180.
- [39] G. Yun, R. V. Ravi, and A. K. Jumani, "Analysis of the teaching quality on deep learning-based innovative ideological political education platform," *Progress in Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 175–186, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s13748-021-00272-0.
- [40] A. S. Rahmatullah, E. Mulyasa, S. Syahrani, F. Pongpalilu, and R. E. Putri, "Digital era 4.0: the contribution to education and student psychology," *Linguistics and Culture Review*, vol. 6, no. S3, pp. 89–107, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.21744/lingcure.v6nS3.2064.
- [41] S. Karmina, B. Dyson, P. Watson, and R. Philpot, "Teacher implementation of cooperative learning in Indonesia: a multiple case study," *Education Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 218, May 2021, doi: 10.3390/educsci11050218.
- [42] J. Koopman, "The restoration of gotong royong as a form of post-disaster solidarity in Lombok, Indonesia," *South East Asia Research*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 279–296, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1080/0967828X.2021.1966318.
- [43] A. F. Nisa, Z. K. Prasetyo, and Istiningih, "The teachings of Ki Hadjar Dewantara in improving the character of elementary school students in the revolution of industry 4.0 era," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Educational Research and Innovation (ICERI 2019)*, Paris, France: Atlantis Press, 2020, pp. 49–56, doi: 10.2991/assehr.k.200204.010.
- [44] D. F. Anwar, "Indonesia and the ASEAN outlook on the Indo-Pacific," *International Affairs*, vol. 96, no. 1, pp. 111–129, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1093/ia/iiz223.
- [45] S. Saiyad, A. Virk, R. Mahajan, and T. Singh, "Online teaching in medical training: establishing good online teaching practices from cumulative experience," *International Journal of Applied and Basic Medical Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 149–155, 2020, doi: 10.4103/ijabmr.IJABMR_358_20.
- [46] B. L. Moorhouse and K. M. Wong, "Blending asynchronous and synchronous digital technologies and instructional approaches to facilitate remote learning," *Journal of Computers in Education*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 51–70, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s40692-021-00195-8.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Rivai M. Simanjuntak is a teacher and served as a Widyaiswara at the current Ministry of Education, Research and Technology, Indonesia. He completed his bachelor of education, majoring in Electrical Engineering, at Medan State University in 1997 and completed his Master of Education at Medan State University in 2010, majoring in Educational Administration. He is an ongoing student in the Doctoral program in the Department of Education Management at Medan State University. His research experience is writing about the Effects of Work Culture, Emotional Intelligence, and Job Satisfaction on Teacher Performance (2010), how Moving classes can increase student achievement motivation, and the Effects of Learning Strategies and Achievement Motivation on Student Achievement (2019). He can be contacted at email: rivaimsimanjuntak@gmail.com.

Sri Milfayetty earned her Bachelor's Degree in Counseling Guidance at the Medan Teachers' Training College (1984), Master's Degree at the Psychology Department, Padjadjaran University, Bandung (1990), and continued her Doctoral Degree majoring in Education Management at Jakarta State University (2010). She is a Psychology and Counseling Guidance Professor at the UNIMED Faculty of Education. Experience in writing scientific articles in journals, including Networking Model in Management Counseling Annual Proceedings of Selected Papers on the Practice of Educational Communications and Technology Presented at the Annual Convention of the Association for Educational Communications and Technology, The Effectiveness of an Integrative Model of Sustainable Collaboration to Improve Counselor Proficiency in Alleviating Client Problems. She can be contacted at email: milfayetty@unimed.ac.id.

Darwin is a Lecturer at the Faculty of Engineering, Universitas Negeri Medan (UNIMED), and currently serves as deputy director of finance at the UNIMED Postgraduate Program. Papers that have been published include: Need Analysis of Junior High School Teachers at Hamparan Perak District, Deli Serdang; Need Analysis and Implementation Training Management Model Development; The Implementation of Management Training Model Diploma in Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, UNIMED; and Reflection of Strategic Management Implementation in Improving the Quality of Education in Sultan Agung, Private Junior High School Pematang Siantar. He can be contacted at email: darwinspi@unimed.ac.id.